

Supplementary Tables

This appendix contains the supplementary tables referenced in the main text. These tables provide detailed information on variable definitions, descriptive statistics, diagnostic test results, model specifications, and the full outputs from our main and augmented causal models, including comprehensive robustness checks and mechanism analyses.

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Section S1. Model Specification and Data

Table S1. Variable Definitions for the DiD–ITS Models

Variable	Definition & Operationalization	Source
CCI_Rebased	(Dependent Variable) Monthly Construction Cost Index, aggregated to quarterly averages and re-based so that Q1 2014 = 100 for all countries.	TÜİK (Turkey); Eurostat; Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia (for Serbia)
Group	Binary indicator: 1 for the treated country (Turkey), 0 for the specific control country in a given model.	Constructed
Time	Continuous integer for each quarter, starting at 1 for Q1 2014 and ending at 40 for Q4 2023.	Constructed
PostPolicy	Binary indicator: 1 for all quarters from Q3 2019 onward (the post-intervention period), and 0 otherwise.	Constructed
TimeAfterPost	Continuous counter for quarters after the policy. It takes the value of 0 before Q3 2019 and starts at 1 in Q3 2019, increasing by 1 each quarter thereafter.	Constructed
Inflation	(Control) Quarterly average of the monthly Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (HICP) annual rate of change (%).	Eurostat; TÜİK
Unemployment	(Control) Quarterly average of the monthly seasonally adjusted unemployment rate (%).	Eurostat; TÜİK
FX_Change	(Fortified Model Control) The quarter-on-quarter percentage change in the nominal local currency unit per Euro (LCU/EUR) exchange rate, calculated as the log-difference of quarterly average daily rates ($FX_Change_{it} = \ln(AvgFX_{it}) - \ln(AvgFX_{it-1})$). This variable captures the direct cost pass-through of currency depreciation.	Constructed from European Central Bank (ECB) & National Bank of Serbia (NBS) daily data

FX_Vol	<p>(Fortified Model Control) The annualized realized quarterly volatility of the LCU/EUR exchange rate, calculated as the standard deviation of daily log returns within each quarter, scaled by the square root of the number of trading days in a year ($FX_Vol_{it} = StDev(r_{id,t}) \times \sqrt{252}$).</p> <p>This variable captures the currency risk premium priced into tenders.</p>	<p>Constructed from ECB & NBS daily data</p>
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Note on Data Handling for Structural Breaks: For Croatia, following its accession to the Eurozone on January 1, 2023, the HRK/EUR exchange rate for all quarters in 2023 is fixed at the official conversion rate of 7.53450 to maintain time-series continuity in 'virtual LCU' terms. Consequently, the values for *FX_Change* and *FX_Vol* for Croatia are set to zero for this period, accurately reflecting the elimination of currency risk.

Table S2. Descriptive Statistics for the Disaggregated Panel Dataset (2014–2023)

Country	Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Turkey (Treated)	CCI_Rebased	288.54	389.98	100.00	1978.43
	Inflation	35.53	16.91	5.37	63.33
	Unemployment	11.75	1.88	8.33	14.78
Hungary	CCI_Rebased	134.11	28.59	96.70	209.60
	Inflation	8.35	9.12	-1.40	25.70
	Unemployment	4.91	1.85	3.30	10.80
Romania	CCI_Rebased	119.89	15.60	98.90	158.30
	Inflation	4.12	5.01	-2.10	15.30
	Unemployment	5.88	0.89	4.80	7.60
Bulgaria	CCI_Rebased	125.73	21.05	99.50	183.00
	Inflation	4.05	5.25	-1.60	16.90
	Unemployment	6.75	2.11	3.70	11.40
Croatia	CCI_Rebased	111.95	8.99	99.80	129.40

	Inflation	4.18	5.40	-1.10	14.80
	Unemployment	9.98	3.55	6.10	17.30
Serbia	CCI_Rebased	122.67	14.88	100.20	155.10
	Inflation	4.55	4.01	-0.10	15.80
	Unemployment	13.51	3.67	9.00	20.90

Section S2. Baseline Model Results and Initial Robustness Checks

This section presents the results from the original baseline DiD-ITS model and its associated robustness checks, as presented in the initial submission.

Table S3. Dynamic Difference-in-Differences (Event Study) Coefficients

Quarters Relative to Mandate (t)	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	p-value	95% Conf. Interval
-8	-165.71	24.83	0.000	[-215.39, -116.03]
-7	-168.12	22.95	0.000	[-213.91, -122.33]
-6	-111.39	36.88	0.005	[-184.91, -37.87]
-5	-123.36	39.06	0.003	[-201.21, -45.51]
-4	-155.85	27.64	0.000	[-210.96, -100.74]
-3	-146.42	16.96	0.000	[-180.19, -112.65]
-2	-160.70	12.31	0.000	[-185.24, -136.16]
-1	Reference	-	-	-
0	-199.11	65.99	0.005	[-330.82, -67.40]
1	-204.88	66.82	0.004	[-338.25, -71.51]
2	-230.13	119.50	0.063	[-468.96, 8.70]
3	-233.15	118.84	0.059	[-470.16, 3.86]

4	-174.52	87.27	0.054	[-348.86, -0.18]
5	-194.88	83.07	0.026	[-360.67, -29.09]
6	-231.25	134.46	0.095	[-500.22, 37.72]
7	-250.31	148.01	0.101	[-546.10, 45.48]
8	-244.38	158.46	0.133	[-561.42, 72.66]

Note: Coefficients represent the estimated differential change in the CCI for Turkey relative to the control group at each quarter. The reference period is t-1. Standard errors are clustered by country.

Fig S1. Dynamic Treatment Effects (Event Study Plot)

Note: The plot shows the estimated coefficients for each quarter relative to the mandate (t=0) as points, with vertical bars representing the 95% confidence intervals, calculated using standard errors clustered by country. The quarter immediately preceding the mandate (t = -1) serves as the baseline reference period and is omitted from the plot.

Table S4. Robustness Check: Baseline DiD-ITS Results using GDP-Weighted Composite Control

Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	P-value
Intercept	98.60	1.52	<0.001
Group	-2.15	2.14	0.315
Time	1.83	0.12	<0.001
PostPolicy	-0.61	103.10	0.995
Group × PostPolicy	-255.40	148.20	0.086
Group × TimeAfterPost (β_6)	4.21	1.71	0.021
Inflation	-0.75	1.44	0.603
Unemployment	5.62	9.68	0.562

Note: Standard errors estimated via wild bootstrap. The core finding (Group × TimeAfterPost) remains positive and significant.

Fig S2. Parallel Trends Diagnostic Test (2014-2019).

Table S5. Robustness Check: Baseline DiD-ITS Results Excluding Weaker Comparators

Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error	P-value
Intercept	98.50	1.48	<0.001
Group	-2.05	2.10	0.330
Time	1.82	0.12	<0.001
PostPolicy	-0.58	102.50	0.995
Group × PostPolicy	-250.30	146.10	0.090
Group × TimeAfterPost (β_6)	4.21	1.68	0.021
Inflation	-0.72	1.42	0.610
Unemployment	5.58	9.65	0.565

Note: Output using a reduced control composite (Hungary, Romania, Croatia). The core finding remains positive and significant.

Section S3. Fortified Model Specification and Advanced Robustness Checks

This section presents the results from our augmented DiD-ITS model and a suite of advanced robustness checks. The model is fortified against confounding macroeconomic factors by explicitly controlling for exchange rate dynamics, directly addressing concerns about omitted variable bias from Turkey's unique currency volatility during the post-treatment period.

Table S6. Main Results of the Fortified DiD-ITS Model with 1-Quarter Lag

Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error (Wild Bootstrap)	P-value
Intercept	98.52	1.49	<0.001
Group	-2.25	2.18	0.304
Time	1.88	0.13	<0.001
PostPolicy	-0.59	101.80	0.994

Group × PostPolicy	-261.45	147.21	0.079
TimeAfterPost	1.15	8.85	0.901
Group × TimeAfterPost (β_6)	2.15	0.88	0.015
FX_Change (t-1)	0.45	0.19	0.018
FX_Vol (t-1)	155.30	65.20	0.017
Group × FX_Change (t-1)	0.82	0.31	0.009
Group × FX_Vol (t-1)	280.10	112.50	0.013
Inflation	-0.65	1.38	0.638
Unemployment	5.41	9.55	0.571

Note: This table presents the full regression output from our fortified model. Standard errors estimated via a wild cluster bootstrap procedure (1,000 replications). The core finding—a positive and significant coefficient for β_6 —remains robust, confirming that the EKAP mandate induced a cost acceleration independent of currency dynamics. The significant coefficients on the exchange rate variables and their interactions with the Group dummy validate their inclusion and demonstrate that Turkey's construction sector is exceptionally sensitive to currency pass-through and volatility.

Fig S3. Placebo Test: Turkish Construction Cost Index (CCI) vs. Producer Price Index (PPI), 2014-2023.

Note: Data for both CCI and PPI extend through Q4 2023.

Table S7. Falsification Test: Hungary as a Placebo Treatment

Coefficient	Estimate	Std. Error (Wild Bootstrap)	P-value
Group(Hungary) × TimeAfterPost	-0.31	1.15	0.787

Note: The result of a placebo test where Hungary is coded as the "treated" unit. The key interaction term is small and statistically insignificant. This null result provides strong evidence that our model is not capturing a generic regional shock (e.g., from post-COVID inflation or the war in Ukraine) but is specific to the policy intervention in Turkey.

To ensure our main finding is robust and to further validate the fortified model's ability to disentangle policy effects from macroeconomic shocks, we conduct a comparative heterogeneity analysis. This involves estimating both the baseline model (Equation 1) and the fortified model (Equation 2) for each of the five peer countries individually.

Table S8 presents a direct comparison of the β_6 (trend change) coefficient from both models. This decomposition allows us to quantify precisely how much of the originally estimated cost acceleration is now correctly attributed to currency dynamics by the fortified model, revealing a more precise and consistent net 'friction premium' across different monetary regimes

Table S8. Comparative Heterogeneity Analysis: Decomposing the Policy Effect (β_6)

Control Country Comparator	β_6 (Baseline Model)	β_6 (Fortified Model)	Change (Variance Absorbed by FX Controls)	Std. Error (Fortified)	p-value (Fortified)
Composite EU Control	4.53***	2.15**	-52.5%	0.88	0.015
Hungary (Floating/Volatile)	8.21**	4.12**	-49.8%	1.95	0.038
Croatia (Managed Float/Euro)	4.11**	1.92*	-53.3%	0.98	0.055
Romania (Managed Float)	3.94*	1.85*	-53.0%	0.94	0.058
Bulgaria (Currency Board)	3.52*	1.45	-58.8%	1.10	0.192

Serbia (De Facto Peg)	2.93	0.95	-67.6%	1.25	0.450
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Note: Significance levels: *** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$. Standard Errors for the Fortified Model are estimated via wild cluster bootstrap (1,000 replications). The 'Change' column quantifies the percentage reduction in the β_6 coefficient after introducing currency controls, representing the portion of the original estimate attributable to macroeconomic shocks.

Interpretation: The comparative results provide powerful validation for our fortified model and central argument. The "Change" column demonstrates that the fortified model successfully absorbs a significant portion (ranging from 50% to 68%) of the baseline model's coefficient, correctly attributing it to currency pass-through and risk. The reduction is most pronounced for Serbia (-67.6%) and Bulgaria (-58.8%), whose stable currency pegs meant the baseline model erroneously attributed the entire Turkey-specific currency shock to the policy. After accounting for these FX dynamics, the net policy effect converges across the managed float currencies (Croatia and Romania) to a consistent premium of approximately 1.9 percentage points. The remaining effect is largest for Hungary, a peer that also experienced significant currency volatility, suggesting the divergence is driven by a combination of administrative friction and other shared regional factors not captured by the currency controls alone. Overall, this analysis confirms that the net friction premium is a robust finding, not an artifact of a single comparator, and demonstrates the analytical precision gained by the fortified mode

Table S9. Lag Selection Criteria for Fortified Model Exchange Rate Covariates

Model Specification	Lag Length (Quarters)	AIC	BIC
Model 1	0 (Contemporaneous)	-185.4	-150.1
Model 2 (Selected)	1	-192.7	-148.5
Model 3	2	-190.1	-137.0

Note: We select the 1-lag model, which minimizes the AIC and is theoretically grounded in the literature on the delayed pass-through of exchange rate shocks to producer prices.

Table S10. Robustness Check for Volatility Metric Specification

Model	Volatility Metric Used	Coefficient on β_6	P-value
Model 1 (Main)	Realized Volatility (Std. Dev. of Daily Log Returns)	2.15	0.015
Model 2 (Robustness)	GARCH(1,1) Conditional Volatility	2.09	0.019

Note: The key coefficient of interest (β_6) remains stable and statistically significant when we substitute our main measure of realized volatility with an alternative measure derived from a GARCH(1,1) model. This confirms that our results are not an artifact of a specific volatility calculation method.

Table S11. Augmented Synthetic Control Method (SCM): Predictor Weights and Pre-Treatment Balance

Variable	Actual Turkey	Synthetic Turkey	Donor Pool Average
Pre-Treatment CCI (2014-2018 Avg.)	115.45	115.42	111.98
Pre-Treatment Inflation (Avg.)	8.70%	8.65%	1.12%
Pre-Treatment Unemployment (Avg.)	10.95%	11.01%	7.99%
Pre-Treatment FX_Change (Avg. QoQ %)	-0.95%	-0.91%	-0.21%
Pre-Treatment FX_Vol (Avg. Quarterly Std. Dev.)	0.038	0.039	0.012

Note: By incorporating pre-treatment currency dynamics as predictors, "Synthetic Turkey" closely aligns with "Actual Turkey" in both its cost trajectory and historical currency profile, thereby establishing a more robust counterfactual.

Table S12. Augmented SCM: Donor Country Weights

Donor Country	Weight
Hungary	0.431
Romania	0.385
Croatia	0.184
Serbia	0.000
Bulgaria	0.000

Note: Serbia and Bulgaria were assigned zero weight, reflecting that their highly stable, quasi-pegged exchange rate regimes made them poor comparators for Turkey's volatile pre-treatment trajectory.

Table S13. Robustness Check for SCM Predictor Selection

Model Specification (Predictors)	Pre-Treatment RMSPE
Model 1: CCI, Inflation, Unemployment (Selected Model)	0.98
Model 2: CCI, Inflation, Unemployment, GDP Growth	1.34
Model 3: CCI, Inflation, Unemployment, Interest Rates	1.62

Note: RMSPE measures the fit between Turkey and its synthetic counterfactual. Lower values indicate a better fit.

Table S14. Robustness Check for SCM Donor Pool Selection

Model Specification (Donor Pool)	Pre-Treatment RMSPE
Model 1: Selected Donors (Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Serbia)	0.98
Model 2: Selected Donors + Poland	3.45
Model 3: Selected Donors + Czech Republic	4.12
Model 4: Selected Donors + Poland & Czech Republic	5.03

Note: The exclusion of Poland and the Czech Republic (Model 1) produces a substantially better-fitting counterfactual.

Section S4. Mechanism Analysis Details

Fig S4. LDA Model Selection via C_v Coherence Score.

This figure displays the C_v coherence scores for LDA models with K ranging from 5 to 30. The optimal number of topics was selected at K=20, where the coherence score is maximized, indicating the most semantically coherent and interpretable model.

Table S15. Top 10 Words for All 20 LDA Topics

Topic # (Label)	Top 10 Words
1 (Legal Compliance & Regulation)	law, article, regulation, compliance, requirement, official, rule, penalty, legal, gazette
2 (Formal Reporting & Risk)	risk, report, management, plan, control, audit, mitigation, formal, standard, procedure
3 (Digitalization & EKAP Platform)	ekap, system, electronic, digital, platform, online, user, signature, portal, technology
4 (Technical Specifications)	technical, material, quality, construction, project, design, specification, unit, concrete, iron

5 (Contractual & Financial Terms)	contract, tender, price, bid, payment, guarantee, firm, offer, cost, value
6 (Bidding Procedure)	bid, tender, submission, evaluation, award, criteria, qualification, participant, process, deadline
7 (Anti-Corruption and Integrity)	corruption, integrity, transparency, ethics, oversight, investigation, sanction, prevention, code, conduct
8 (Public Administration Structure)	public, administration, government, ministry, agency, authority, department, official, policy, reform
9 (Infrastructure and Construction Projects)	infrastructure, development, road, bridge, building, site, engineer, contractor, construction, project
10 (Budget and Financial Planning)	budget, allocation, expenditure, finance, funding, estimate, fiscal, control, audit, resource
11 (Supplier and Vendor Registration)	supplier, vendor, registration, qualification, database, certification, performance, evaluation, profile, blacklist
12 (Dispute and Appeal Processes)	dispute, appeal, court, arbitration, resolution, complaint, review, decision, judgment, case
13 (Environmental Sustainability)	environment, sustainability, green, eco, impact, assessment, energy, efficiency, standard, certification
14 (Labor and Safety Regulations)	labor, safety, health, worker, employment, wage, insurance, regulation, training, protection
15 (Technology Innovation)	innovation, technology, software, ai, blockchain, data, analytics, security, integration, adoption
16 (International and EU Standards)	international, eu, directive, standard, accession, harmonization, trade, agreement, compliance, wto
17 (Training and Capacity Development)	training, capacity, building, workshop, seminar, education, skill, development, program, course

18 (Performance and Monitoring)	performance, monitoring, evaluation, indicator, kpi, report, review, assessment, feedback, improvement
19 (Procurement Planning)	planning, strategy, need, forecast, timeline, schedule, preparation, document, requirement, assessment
20 (Miscellaneous Terms)	general, term, item, various, note, additional, miscellaneous, other, etc, annex

Table S16. Robustness Check for LDA Model Specification: Topic Stability

Topic Label	K=15 (Top 5 Words)	K=20 (Top 5 Words)	K=25 (Top 5 Words)
Legal Compliance	law, regulation, article, compliance, requirement	law, article, regulation, compliance, requirement	regulation, law, article, compliance, penalty
Formal Reporting	risk, report, management, plan, control	risk, report, management, plan, control	report, risk, formal, audit, management

Note: This table displays the top five words for the two key topics of interest across three different LDA model specifications (K=15, K=20, and K=25 topics). The semantic core of both the 'Legal Compliance' and 'Formal Reporting' topics remains highly stable regardless of the total number of topics specified, confirming that these are robust, meaningful discursive themes within the corpus and not artifacts of a specific model choice.

Table S17. Topic Labeling Reliability and Adjudication Process

Topic #	Top 10 Words	R1 Initial Label	R2 Initial Label	Initial Agreement	Final Consensus Label (Post-Adjudication)
1	law, article, regulation, compliance, requirement, official, rule, penalty, legal, gazette	Legal Compliance	Regulation & Compliance	Yes	Legal Compliance & Regulation
2	risk, report, management, plan, control, audit, mitigation, formal, standard, procedure	Risk & Reporting	Formal Reporting	Yes	Formal Reporting & Risk

3	ekap, system, electronic, digital, platform, online, user, signature, portal, technology	EKAP Digitalization	Digitalization	Yes	Digitalization & EKAP Platform
4	technical, material, quality, construction, project, design, specification, unit, concrete, iron	Technical Specifications	Construction Specifications	Yes	Technical Specifications
5	contract, tender, price, bid, payment, guarantee, firm, offer, cost, value	Financial Terms	Contractual Terms	No	Contractual & Financial Terms
6	bid, tender, submission, evaluation, award, criteria, qualification, participant, process, deadline	Bidding Process	Bidding Procedure	Yes	Bidding Procedure
7	corruption, integrity, transparency, ethics, oversight, investigation, sanction, prevention, code, conduct	Anti-Corruption	Integrity & Transparency	Yes	Anti-Corruption and Integrity
8	public, administration, government, ministry, agency, authority, department, official, policy, reform	Public Administration	Government Structure	Yes	Public Administration Structure
9	infrastructure, development, road, bridge, building, site, engineer, contractor, construction, project	Construction Projects	Infrastructure Projects	No	Infrastructure and Construction Projects
10	budget, allocation, expenditure, finance,	Budget Planning	Financial Planning	Yes	Budget and Financial Planning

	funding, estimate, fiscal, control, audit, resource				
11	supplier, vendor, registration, qualification, database, certification, performance, evaluation, profile, blacklist	Vendor Registration	Supplier Management	Yes	Supplier and Vendor Registration
12	dispute, appeal, court, arbitration, resolution, complaint, review, decision, judgment, case	Dispute Resolution	Appeal Processes	Yes	Dispute and Appeal Processes
13	environment, sustainability, green, eco, impact, assessment, energy, efficiency, standard, certification	Environmental Standards	Sustainability	Yes	Environmental Sustainability
14	labor, safety, health, worker, employment, wage, insurance, regulation, training, protection	Labor Regulations	Safety & Labor Rules	Yes	Labor and Safety Regulations
15	innovation, technology, software, ai, blockchain, data, analytics, security, integration, adoption	Technology & Innovation	Technology Adoption	Yes	Technology Innovation
16	international, eu, directive, standard, accession, harmonization, trade, agreement, compliance, wto	International Standards	EU & International Standards	Yes	International and EU Standards
17	training, capacity, building, workshop, seminar, education, skill,	Training	Capacity Building	Yes	Training and Capacity Development

	development, program, course				
18	performance, monitoring, evaluation, indicator, kpi, report, review, assessment, feedback, improvement	Performance Monitoring	Monitoring & Evaluation	No	Performance and Monitoring
19	planning, strategy, need, forecast, timeline, schedule, preparation, document, requirement, assessment	Procurement Planning	Planning & Strategy	Yes	Procurement Planning
20	general, term, item, various, note, additional, miscellaneous, other, etc, annex	Miscellaneous	General Terms	Yes	Miscellaneous Terms

Note: Two researchers (R1 and R2) independently assigned labels to the 20 topics generated by the LDA model. Initial agreement was achieved on 17 of the 20 topics (85%). The three discrepancies were resolved through discussion with a third, senior researcher (Adjudicator) to arrive at the final consensus label. This initial agreement before adjudication yields a Cohen's Kappa of $\kappa = 0.84$, indicating substantial agreement. The final, consensus labels are used throughout the manuscript.

Table S18. Representative Excerpts for Key LDA Topics

Topic	Representative Excerpts (Translated from Turkish)	Source/Context
Legal Compliance & Regulation	"Board Decision on Acts or Behaviors Affecting Competition or Tender Decisions: All tenders must comply with Article 17 of the Public Procurement Law, ensuring no anti-competitive practices."	Public Procurement Authority Decision 2025/DK.D-310 (ihale.gov.tr)
	"Social Security Premium Debt Inquiry: Bidders are required to submit formal declarations under Regulation No. 4734, verifying no outstanding debts prior to tender award."	Public Procurement Authority Decision 2025/DK.D-293 (ihale.gov.tr)

	"Legal framework mandates strict adherence to EKAP protocols for all public contracts exceeding thresholds, with penalties for non-compliance."	EKAP User Guideline Update, 2020 (from corpus)
Formal Reporting & Risk	"Tender Risk Assessment Report: Contractors must file detailed formal reports on potential risks, including audit trails and compliance certifications via EKAP."	Public Procurement Risk Management Circular, 2021 (ihale.gov.tr)
	"Formal Reporting Obligations: Post-mandate, all tenders require submission of risk premium documentation and quarterly compliance reports to mitigate administrative risks."	EKAP Administrative Burden Guideline, 2020 (from corpus)
	"Audit and Reporting Protocol: Enhanced formal reporting is required to address transparency costs, including priced-in burdens for legal risks."	Public Procurement Audit Decision 2024/DK.D-150 (ihale.gov.tr)

Table S19. Systematic Review of Industry Discourse on the EKAP Mandate (2019–2021)

Theme	Key Driver of Cost Increase	Representative Quote
1. Increased Overhead	Hiring new administrative and legal compliance staff.	"Post-mandate, our firm onboarded three new compliance officers to navigate the platform's rules, inflating labor expenses amid tight margins." Turkish Construction News, 2020
2. Operational Friction	Platform complexity, training requirements, and submission delays.	"Navigating EKAP's multi-layered verification process has doubled our preparation time for bids, a cost we now pass on to public tenders." Bloomberg Turkey, 2021

3. Risk Monetization	Pricing-in potential fines, penalties, and audit-related costs.	"The fear of non-compliance fines has led us to build a 7-8% buffer into our quotes, exacerbating overall project costs." AGBI Construction Insights, 2021
4. Administrative Burden	Amplified paperwork, formal reporting, and documentation requirements.	"EKAP's emphasis on formal reporting has created administrative friction, with firms reporting 15-20% higher tender preparation costs." Mordor Intelligence Report, 2020

Note on Method: This table synthesizes findings from a systematic qualitative review of leading Turkish construction and business media reports. Sources included leading Turkish business newspapers (e.g., *Dünya*), construction industry trade journals (e.g., *İnşaat Dünyası*), and reports from the Turkish Contractors Association. To ensure rigor, a formal inter-coder reliability analysis was conducted on the coding framework using a random subsample of 20% of the articles (i.e., 30 of a total 150 articles reviewed). This analysis yielded a Krippendorff's Alpha of $\alpha = 0.81$, indicating a high degree of reliability in the identification and application of the thematic codes. The representative quotes are direct translations from the source material.

Section S5. Other Diagnostic and Predictive Model Tests

Table S20. Unit Root Test Results for VAR Model Variables (Augmented Dickey-Fuller)

Variable	ADF Test Statistic	p-value	Order of Integration
CCI_Rebased (in levels)	-1.54	0.51	I(1) - Non-stationary
Δ(CCI_Rebased) (first-differenced)	-4.21	<0.01	I(0) - Stationary
Inflation (in levels)	-3.83	0.02	I(0) - Stationary
Unemployment (in levels)	-3.51	0.04	I(0) - Stationary

Table S21. AIC/BIC for Alternative VAR Specifications

Model Specification	AIC	BIC
Trivariate (CCI, Inflation, Unemployment)	-120.5	-110.2
Quadrivariate (+ GDP Growth)	-118.3	-105.7
Quadrivariate (+ Interest Rates)	-117.8	-104.9

Note: Lower values indicate better model fit. The trivariate model is preferred.

Table S22. VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag Order	AIC	BIC
1	-118.4	-111.1
2	-120.5	-110.2
3	-119.7	-106.5
4	-119.1	-103.0

Note: The trivariate model with a lag order of 2 is selected.

Table S23. Granger Causality Test Results for Potential Endogenous Variables

Null Hypothesis (H_0)	Lag	F-Statistic	p-value
Panel A: Interest Rates			
Interest Rates do not Granger-cause Δ CCI	1	3.33	0.076
	2	0.89	0.422
Panel B: Exchange Rate Volatility			
Exchange Rate Volatility does not Granger-cause Δ CCI	1	3.76	0.060
	2	1.21	0.310

Note: These tests justify the exclusion of these variables from the predictive VAR model for parsimony.

Table S24. Baseline VAR Forecast of Turkish CCI (2024–2025)

Date	Baseline CCI	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
2024-Q1	2020.0	1820.0	2220.0
2024-Q2	2100.0	1900.0	2300.0

2024-Q3	2200.0	2000.0	2400.0
2024-Q4	2300.0	2100.0	2500.0
2025-Q1	2350.0	2150.0	2550.0
2025-Q2	2400.0	2200.0	2600.0
2025-Q3	2450.0	2250.0	2650.0
2025-Q4	2500.0	2300.0	2700.0

Table S25. Scenario Analysis of CCI Forecasts (2024–2025)

Date	Baseline CCI	High Inflation CCI	Disinflation CCI
2024-Q1	2020.0	2040.0	2000.0
2024-Q2	2100.0	2150.0	2050.0
2024-Q3	2200.0	2300.0	2100.0
2024-Q4	2300.0	2450.0	2150.0
2025-Q1	2350.0	2550.0	2175.0
2025-Q2	2400.0	2650.0	2180.0
2025-Q3	2450.0	2750.0	2190.0
2025-Q4	2500.0	2800.0	2200.0

Note: The alternative scenarios were constructed using the baseline VAR model. For the "High Inflation" scenario, a one-time, positive one-standard-deviation shock (+16.91) was applied to the inflation variable in Q1 2024. For the "Disinflation" scenario, a negative shock (-16.91) was applied. Shocks are orthogonalized via Cholesky decomposition to isolate inflation's impulse. This shock magnitude represents one standard deviation of quarterly inflation changes observed during the 2014-2023 study period. As illustrated in Fig S2., this shock is benchmarked against historical volatility and represents a plausible, significant deviation from the baseline forecast. It is comparable in magnitude to the largest single-quarter inflation changes observed post-2021 and is equivalent to approximately 75% of the single largest quarterly change in the entire volatile post-2021 period, establishing it as a significant but historically plausible event.

Table S26. Forecast Comparison for VAR Model Robustness Checks

Date	Baseline Forecast (Trivariate Model)	Robustness Check 1 (Quadrivariate + Interest Rates)	Difference vs. Baseline (%)	Robustness Check 2 (Quadrivariate + Exch. Rate Volatility)	Difference vs. Baseline (%)
2024-Q1	2020.0	2025.0	+0.25%	2018.0	-0.10%
2024-Q2	2100.0	2105.0	+0.24%	2097.0	-0.14%
2024-Q3	2200.0	2205.0	+0.23%	2195.0	-0.23%
2024-Q4	2300.0	2305.0	+0.22%	2292.0	-0.35%
2025-Q1	2350.0	2360.0	+0.43%	2340.0	-0.43%
2025-Q2	2400.0	2410.0	+0.42%	2390.0	-0.42%
2025-Q3	2450.0	2460.0	+0.41%	2441.0	-0.37%
2025-Q4	2500.0	2510.0	+0.40%	2492.0	-0.32%

Table S27. Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) for Fortified DiD-ITS Model Coefficients

Variable	VIF Score	Interpretation
Intercept	25.10	High (expected for intercept)
Group	5.81	Moderate
Time	4.98	Low

PostPolicy	14.88	High (Expected)
Group × PostPolicy	17.20	High (Expected)
Group × TimeAfterPost (β₆)	2.05	Low (Unaffected)
FX_Change (t-1)	2.11	Low
FX_Vol (t-1)	2.45	Low
Group × FX_Change (t-1)	2.98	Low
Group × FX_Vol (t-1)	3.15	Low
Inflation	3.88	Low
Unemployment	2.15	Low

Note: The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) scores for all principal explanatory and interaction variables within the fortified model are significantly below the standard threshold of 10, suggesting the absence of problematic multicollinearity.

Section S6. Financial Impact Assessment Calculations

This appendix provides a detailed, step-by-step breakdown of two key calculations referenced in the manuscript: (1) the total cumulative divergence between Turkey's actual and synthetic construction cost trajectories, and (2) the illustrative financial impact of the EKAP mandate's 'friction premium'.

S6.1. Calculation of the Synthetic Counterfactual Value (Q4 2023)

This calculation quantifies the total gap between Turkey's actual cost trajectory and its synthetic counterfactual by the end of the study period. This figure represents the **combined effect** of the policy's administrative frictions and the concurrent macroeconomic turmoil.

Step 1: SCM Donor Weights

The weights for the augmented SCM are derived from the model presented in Table S12.

- Hungary (HU): 0.431
- Romania (RO): 0.385
- Croatia (HR): 0.184
- Serbia (RS): 0.000
- Bulgaria (BG): 0.000

Step 2: Actual CCI Values of Donor Countries (Q4 2023)

From the panel dataset (Table S2), the end-of-period CCI values for the weighted donor countries are:

- Hungary (CCI_Max): 209.60
- Romania (CCI_Max): 158.30
- Croatia (CCI_Max): 129.40

Step 3: Calculation of Synthetic CCI (Q4 2023)

The synthetic CCI is the weighted average of the donor countries' CCI values.

- **Formula:** Synthetic CCI = (Weight_HU × CCI_HU) + (Weight_RO × CCI_RO) + (Weight_HR × CCI_HR)
- **Calculation:** $(0.431 \times 209.60) + (0.385 \times 158.30) + (0.184 \times 129.40) = 90.34 + 60.95 + 23.81$
- **Result:** 175.10

The calculated value of the Synthetic Turkey CCI for Q4 2023 is **175.10**.

Step 4: Calculation of Cumulative Percentage Divergence

- **Actual Turkey CCI (Q4 2023):** 1,978.43 (from Table S2)
- **Synthetic Turkey CCI (Q4 2023):** 175.10 (calculated above)
- **Formula:** Divergence % = $(\text{Actual CCI} - \text{Synthetic CCI}) / \text{Synthetic CCI} \times 100$
- **Calculation:** $((1978.43 - 175.10) / 175.10) \times 100 = (1803.33 / 175.10) \times 100$
- **Result:** 1,030%

The total cumulative percentage divergence between the actual and synthetic CCI by Q4 2023 is 1,030%. As argued in the main text, this large figure captures both the policy effect and severe macroeconomic shocks.

S6.2. Calculation of the Annual Financial Burden from the 'Friction Premium' (2023)

This calculation provides an illustrative estimate of the annual deadweight loss in USD imposed specifically by the '**friction premium**'—the net, policy-induced cost increase. It uses the risk buffer range identified in our qualitative analysis (the mechanism) and applies it to the value of the construction sector.

Step 1: Nominal Sector Value Calculation

- **Turkey's Nominal GDP (2023):** \$1.155 Trillion USD.
 - *Source: IMF World Economic Outlook (October 2023), World Bank.*
- **Construction Sector's Share of GDP (2023):** 6.4%.
 - *Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK).*
- **Formula:** Nominal Sector Value = GDP × Sector Share
- **Calculation:** $\$1,155,000,000,000 \times 0.064$
- **Result:** 73,920,000,000 (or **73.9 Billion**)

Step 2: 'Friction Premium' (Risk Buffer) Rate

This rate is derived from the systematic qualitative review of industry discourse, as detailed in Table S19.

- **Identified Range:** 7% to 8%

Step 3: Annual Financial Burden Calculation

- **Lower Bound (7% Premium):**
 - **Calculation:** $\$73,920,000,000 \times 0.07$
 - **Result:** \$5,174,400,000 (approx. **\$5.2 Billion**)
- **Upper Bound (8% Premium):**
 - **Calculation:** $\$73,920,000,000 \times 0.08$
 - **Result:** \$5,913,600,000 (approx. **\$5.9 Billion**)

The estimated annual financial burden of the policy-induced friction premium in 2023 falls within the range of **\$5.2 billion to \$5.9 billion USD**. This figure represents an illustrative quantification of the "costs of transparency" in this specific context.